

EXPLORING THE NEXUS BETWEEN GREEN FINANCING, GREEN HOUSE GAS EMISSIONS AND SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study explored the relationship between green financing, greenhouse gas emissions, and sustainable economic development in Nigeria using secondary data. The research applied a Vector Auto-Regressive model and Granger causality tests. Results showed that green bonds, green credit, renewable energy, and eco-innovation positively influenced sustainable economic development, while green insurance had a positive but insignificant effect. Conversely, greenhouse gas emissions and governance quality negatively impacted growth. The findings highlight the role of green financing in reducing emissions and the need for strong regulatory oversight. The study recommends developing a robust institutional framework, improving regulations on environmental and social financial decisions, and mandating green insurance for high-pollution industries. Additionally, it suggests incentivizing insurance companies to create innovative green insurance products, subsidizing premiums, and promoting capacity-building for financial professionals. The study calls for collaboration among the government, financial institutions, and civil society to support Nigeria's transition to a low-carbon economy.

Keywords: Climate change and Green financing, Greenhouse gas emissions, Governance, Renewable energy production.
JEL Classification: G28, Q54, Q56, Q58

1.0 Introduction

The world is grappling with climate change, environmental degradation, and sustainable development (IPCC, 2014). Green finance has emerged as a vital tool to address these challenges by integrating environmental considerations into financial decision-making (UNEP, 2016). Green finance encompasses financial activities that support environmentally sustainable projects and initiatives. This includes investments in renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable agriculture, funding of ecologically friendly, socially responsible projects, and green technologies. It evaluates assets and risk, facilitates trade, mobilizes savings, and evaluates investments' profitability. Green finance endeavors to develop methods and approaches to identify, evaluate, and integrate risks that emanate from climate change into businesses and project management decision-making process (Odili, Ezeudu, & Ifenkwe, 2024). Green finance is imperative in leading the economy towards sustainable economic development because they assist in

initiatives to reduce CO₂ emissions and promote green growth (Zhang & Wang, 2021). There are three ways green finance lowers CO₂ emissions. It encourages the energy transition and promotes the consumption of renewable energy. The production of renewable energy in place of non-renewable energy mitigates harmful emissions (Chien et al., 2021). Secondly, Green finance encourages energy efficiency, that is, reduces the use of fossil fuel (Pimonenko et al., 2020). Third, Green finance encourages absorption of existing CO₂ emissions from the air (Kamarudin et al., 2021). The reduction of CO₂ emissions as a result of green financing secures the environment from destruction and ensures social well-being (Haroon et al., 2021).

The Nigerian government issued the first sovereign green bond in Africa in December 2017, worth ₦10.69 billion (approximately USD 28 million), and a second green bond series in 2019, worth ₦25 billion (approximately \$65 USD) (FMDQ, 2020; World Bank Climate Knowledge Portal, 2022). Nigeria also launched its Green Bond Market Development Program in 2018, and in 2019, the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) listed over ₦49 billion in green bonds (Sustainable Banking Network Taskforce Report, 2020). Nigeria's green finance market is growing, with \$1.2 billion in green bonds issued between 2019 and 2022 (Adeyeye, 2022). Renewable energy accounts for 10% of Nigeria's energy mix with a target of 30% by 2030 (Nigeria's National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy, 2015). Greenhouse gas emissions in Nigeria are projected to increase by 50% by 2030 (UNEP, 2020). Nigeria's National Climate Change Policy in 2012 sets a target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 20% by 2030 (UNFCCC, 2020). The Nigerian government has implemented policies to promote renewable energy, including tax incentives and feed-in tariffs (Nigeria's National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy, 2015).

In addition, the Nigerian government has invested \$1 billion in renewable energy projects between 2019 and 2022 (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2022). Private sector investment in green finance has grown, with \$500 million invested in 2020 alone (African Development Bank, 2022). International organizations, such as the World Bank and African Development Bank, have provided funding for green finance initiatives in Nigeria (World Bank, 2022). Some programs launched by the Nigerian government to enhance green growth include Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Program (REEEP) aimed at increasing renewable energy capacity by 1,000 MW by 2025 (REEEP, 2022), the CBN's Green Finance Initiative which provides financing for green projects, with a focus on renewable energy and energy efficiency (CBN, 2022), the Green Bond Advisory Committee to promote green bond issuance (Nigerian Stock Exchange, 2022).

The financial sector plays a crucial role in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs) in Nigeria (Adeyeye & Adenuga, 2020). However, the sector's current practices and policies often prioritize short-term gains over long-term sustainability (Ozili, 2020). Green finance can help mitigate this by promoting investments in environment-friendly projects, reducing emissions, and supporting sustainable economic development (World Bank, 2019). Nigeria's green finance market is still nascent and fully untapped, but growing steadily, the government and environmental authorities have been making strides in promoting green finance through various regulations and initiatives, as they recognize the importance of integrating sustainability into their financial sector to address environmental challenges and promote sustainable development.

Policy framework for addressing climate change and reducing greenhouse gas emissions includes the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), which is Nigeria's commitment to reducing greenhouse gas emissions under the Paris Agreement. Nigeria developed its NDC in 2015 towards the ratification of the Paris Agreement on Climate Change aimed at reducing its greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions intensity of GDP by 20% by 2030 relative to the emissions intensity of GDP in the base period 2010 to 2014 on an unconditional basis as well as a further 45% on a conditional basis consequent upon receiving climate finance, technology transfer and capacity building from the developed countries. Alongside, Nigeria developed a comprehensive

Long-Term-Low-Emission Development Strategy (LT-LEDS) to advance its effort towards achieving global commitments after the first submission of the Long-Term Vision 2050 in 2021 at COP 26 in Glasgow as part of its commitment to the Paris Agreement (PA). Carbon pricing is largely regarded as one

of the most effective and simple methods for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG). Developed and developing countries are developing carbon pricing mechanisms to support the implementation of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). Nigeria has, over the years, shown increasing interest in reducing its emissions and has, in its 2018 Gas Flare Commercialization Programme, introduced the payment regime (polluters' pay), which mimics the Carbon Tax. In the updated NDC submitted in 2021, based on the new mitigation analysis, "Nigeria restates its commitment to its unconditional target to reduce GHG emissions by 20% below business-as-usual by 2030, and increases its conditional target to 47% below business-as-usual by 2030 on the condition of receiving appropriate support. All these initiatives are pointers to Nigeria's efforts in reducing its GHG emissions.

Environmental governance advocates sustainability as the supreme condition for the management of all human activities, be it social, economic, or political. Sustainable environmental governance is the management of the environment in such a way that ensures that natural resources are conserved rather than being endangered, and that the environment is preserved for present and future generations (UNEP, 2020). It is a governing model that seeks to increase the availability of life, goods, and services. The challenge of environmental degradation can only be solved effectively by emphasizing the inclusion of the protection of the environment in economic goals to ensure the attainment of environmental sustainability. A Legal framework for sustainable environmental governance will give a legal definition of the term 'sustainability' and provide the necessary legal platform to enable the implementation of global environmental agenda and to secure legal compliance (Biermann & Pattberg, 2019; Adelman, 2019).

Nigeria's reliance on fossil fuels and lack of green finance initiatives hinder its ability to mitigate climate change and achieve sustainable development. Researchers such as (Ranjan (2021), Tang (2020), (Adedayo and Oguntuase 2019), and (Mohammed and Kaushal 2018) focused on the growth of green finance and its effect on the environment and ignored the effect of green finance on the sustainability of the economy. Mills (2009) on the other hand, examined how the insurance industry responded to climate change and found that, despite the insurance sector's significant contribution to the fight against climate change, there are limitations on the risks that insurers can cover While, (Alege, et al. 2016) investigated the direction of causal relationships among emissions, energy consumption and economic growth in Nigeria and Granger causality test indicates existence of unidirectional causation running from fossil fuel to CO₂ emissions and gross domestic product (GDP) per capita Majority of these studies used varying parameters such as CO₂ emissions, environment a legislation and green infrastructural development to measure environmental sustainability and economic growth and produced conflicting results. None of the studies reviewed looked at green financing as a factor that can influence real GDP per capita (the indicator for sustainable economic development). Similarly, the studies did not see greenhouse gas emissions as a mediator variable and governance (regulatory quality) as a moderator variable that could determine the effectiveness of green financing in enhancing sustainable economic development. There is, therefore dearth of empirical studies in Nigeria on the impact of green finance and greenhouse gas emissions on sustainable economic development.

This study investigates the impact of green bond, green credit, green insurance, renewable energy production, eco-innovation, greenhouse gas emissions and governance on sustainable economic development in Nigeria; constructs an index system of green financing and sustainable economic development as part of the efforts aimed at reducing global warming and other environmental footprints from human activities; and proffers policy recommendations for sustainable green finance market to ensure adequate eco-friendly investments, and enhance sustainable economic development. There is therefore, need to address the issue of climate change vulnerability, including environmental and economic challenges facing Nigeria. Nigeria's high levels of greenhouse gas emissions and unsustainable economic development necessitate innovative solutions. Green finance emerged as a crucial tool for mitigating climate change and achieving sustainable economic development. Green financing has the potential to address Nigeria's sustainability challenges, but its effectiveness in Nigeria is not well understood. This study contributes to resolving the crisis of environmental challenges, and the climate change impact on human eco-systems and livelihood, and to safeguard current and future generations by using green financing to enhance sustainable economic development in Nigeria. The study's focus on regulatory quality

and eco-innovation provides valuable insights into the factors that enhance the effectiveness of green finance policies. The study's findings inform policy decisions and contribute to the development of effective green financing initiatives in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria is highly vulnerable to the adverse effects of climate change, as evidenced by rising greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, environmental degradation, and increasing climate-related economic shocks. Despite global and national commitments to reduce emissions and promote sustainable development, Nigeria continues to rely heavily on fossil fuels for energy production and economic activities. This dependence has contributed significantly to the growth of GHG emissions, which are projected to rise substantially by 2030, thereby threatening environmental sustainability, public health, and long-term economic stability. The persistence of high emissions raises concerns about Nigeria's ability to achieve sustainable economic development while meeting its international climate obligations.

Although green finance has emerged globally as a key mechanism for addressing climate change and supporting sustainable development, its practical effectiveness in Nigeria remains uncertain. While the Nigerian government and private sector have introduced initiatives such as green bonds, green credit schemes, and renewable energy investments, these efforts are still relatively limited in scale and impact. The green finance market in Nigeria is nascent, fragmented, and constrained by weak institutional capacity, limited investor confidence, and inadequate regulatory enforcement. As a result, green financing has not yet translated into significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions or sustained improvements in economic development outcomes. Another critical problem is the disconnect between environmental policies and economic performance. Nigeria has developed several policy frameworks, including the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), Long-Term Low Emission Development Strategy (LT-LEDS), and renewable energy policies. However, the effectiveness of these policies is often undermined by weak governance, regulatory inefficiencies, and inconsistent implementation. Poor regulatory quality limits the ability of green finance instruments to channel funds efficiently into environmentally sustainable and economically productive sectors, thereby reducing their potential contribution to sustainable economic development.

Furthermore, eco-innovation is increasingly recognized as a critical mechanism through which green finance can enhance economic performance while reducing environmental harm. Yet, the extent to which green bonds, green credit, and green insurance actually stimulate eco-innovation and support low-carbon technologies remains insufficiently explored, particularly in developing regions. At the same time, continued growth in greenhouse gas emissions raises concerns about whether green finance initiatives are adequately aligned with emissions-reduction objectives or whether they merely coexist with environmentally damaging economic activities.

Empirically, there is a notable gap in the Nigerian literature regarding the integrated analysis of green finance, greenhouse gas emissions, and sustainable economic development. Existing studies have largely examined green finance and environmental outcomes or economic growth in isolation, producing mixed and sometimes conflicting results. Few studies have considered greenhouse gas emissions as a mediating variable through which green finance affects sustainable economic development, or governance as a moderating factor influencing this relationship. Moreover, the use of real GDP per capita as an indicator of sustainable economic development in relation to green finance has been largely neglected.

This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by providing empirical evidence on the nexus between green financing, greenhouse gas emissions, governance, and sustainable economic development in Nigeria. By addressing these issues, the study aims to inform policy formulation and contribute to the design of more effective green finance strategies capable of reducing emissions and promoting long-term sustainable economic growth.

Review of Literature

Two theoretical constructs explained the interrelationship between green finance and greenhouse gas emissions on one hand, and green finance and sustainable economic development on the other hand. First, the Stakeholders Theory, propounded by Freeman (1984), argued that financial institutions must play an important role in the transition to environmental sustainability for society to combat the climate change syndrome. This implies that financial institutions should integrate the sustainability concept into their

financial analysis and investment portfolios. Managers must therefore meet the needs of the host community, employees, and government agencies. Second, the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis (Grossman & Krueger, 1991), postulates that the relationship between economic growth (measured by GDP per capita) and environmental degradation (measured by pollution or resource depletion) follows an inverted U-shaped curve. The EKC hypothesis suggests that in the early stages of economic growth, environmental degradation increases as GDP per capita rises (ascending part of the curve), and as GDP per capita continues to grow, environmental degradation eventually reaches a peak and then begins to decline (descending part of the curve). Green financing provides the necessary funding for the transition to technologies and more sustainable practices, which is critical for reaching the descending part of the EKC. Green financing incentivizes investments in eco-friendly projects, reducing pollution and environmental degradation, and supporting the EKC hypothesis’s prediction of improved environmental outcomes at higher income levels. By providing financing for eco-friendly projects, and encouraging environmentally responsible investments, green finance can help economies move along the EKC, reducing environmental degradation and achieving sustainable economic development.

Based on these theories, this study conceptualized green financing as green bond, green credit, green insurance, investments in renewable energy production, and eco-innovation, while greenhouse gas emissions is the mediator variable and governance (regulatory quality), the moderator variable. Our view in this research referred to as the “integrated view”, held that the goal of sustainable development is to ensure both the well-being of those currently living and the potential for the well-being of future generations. Secondly, this study examined sustainable development from the concept of sustainable economic development. Thus, real GDP per capita was chosen as the indicator for sustainable economic development.

The conceptual framework is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Authors’ 2024

Body of literature exists to explain interrelationship between green finance, greenhouse gas emissions and economic growth and development, and they include a study by (Mui Yin, Sheue Li, Boon Yann, & Chin Hong 2024) that sort to know if green financing plays a significant role in mitigating environmental degradation in the BRI region. Utilizing a Generalized Method of Moments approach, they found green finance is negatively and significantly correlated with environmental degradation, suggesting green financing plays an essential role in reducing the deterioration of environmental quality, while enhancing economic growth at the same time. (Ehiedu and Eyamu 2023) Their study analyzed green financing initiatives (GFI) and economic stability in Nigeria from 1989 to 2021. The study used Robust Least Square-RLS analysis on secondary data obtained from the World Bank Pollution Management database and the Central Bank of Nigeria-CBN Statistical Bulletin. The RLS tests revealed that both Green Prevention Costs-GNPC and Green Internal Failure Costs-GNIC have significant effect on the economic stability of

Nigeria. However, Green Evaluation Costs had insignificant effect on economic stability of Nigeria. Hence, the study concludes that GFI (Green Prevention Costs and Green Internal Failure Costs) had a high predictive effect on the stability of the Nigerian economy. In the same vein, (Monday and Chukwuemeka 2023) appraised the level of commitment of financial institutions, and construction professionals towards green infrastructural development in Nigeria through green finance implementation using a survey design approach. The result showed that there is a high level of awareness of green financing practices among construction professionals and financial institutions.

The level of awareness however, differs from implementation of green finance practices, which was low in infrastructure development in Nigeria. Similarly, (Oriakhi, 2021) used data on flared gases obtained from emission inventory for the Niger Delta region (NGR) to evaluate the impact of GHGs emissions on sustainable economic development of the NGR. Empirical formula, as well as emission factors collected from existing literature and secondary data sourced from the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation, were used to estimate GHGs and black carbon inventory for the region. Out of 555.74 billion cubic meters of gas flared between 1990 and 2014, an estimated 1.80×10^9 tons of Carbon (IV) Oxide equivalent was released to the atmosphere. Emission uncertainty measured in relative terms was between -92.2% and 51.16% . The emission volumes reduced by 49.71% in 2014 to 3.61×10^7 tCO₂ tCO₂e relative to the volume of emission in 1990. The findings also demonstrate that the commendable success made by the country in reducing greenhouse and black carbon emissions has been driven by improved gas utilization nationwide, which directly reduces the volume of gas flared amid oil companies' activities in the region.

(Erhun, 2015) proposed a legal framework for sustainable environmental governance that will serve as a bedrock for the socio-economic development in Nigeria. The focus of their study was on how to attain a framework that will promote sound environmental governance and the attainment of a sustainable society in Nigeria. The study found that Nigeria enjoys a comparatively well-established body of laws and a full-fledged ministry to regulate the Nigerian environment but despite all measures put in place to safe-guard Nigerian environmental space, Nigeria is experiencing regulatory failure in environmental governance and the ability to handle same has continued to dwindle in spite efforts and that economic development is priced over and above the sustainability of the environment. Environmental concerns are not faithfully integrated into economic development plans in such a manner as to positively influence behavior in any significant and concluded that sustainable governance in environmental matters is lacking in Nigeria.

Methodology

Secondary data were compiled from the CBN Statistical Bulletin, Nigeria Insurance Industry (NIID) database, National Climate Data Center (NCDC), Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), and World Development Indicators (WDI) database. The study period ranges from 2000 to 2022. The variables used are Real gross domestic product per capita (RGDPpc– independent variable; and Green bond (GB), Green credit (GC), Green insurance (GI), Renewable energy production (REP), Eco-innovation (EI), Greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), and Regulatory quality (RQ) as independent variables. These variables represent key components of green financing. By using these independent variables, the article provided a nuanced understanding of the policy implications for promoting green financing, reducing emissions, and achieving sustainable economic development in Nigeria. Using E-Views 10 software, Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) was employed on the Vector Auto-Regressive (VAR) model. MLE is a method for estimating the parameters of a statistical model (β_0 , β_1 , and σ^2 in this case) by finding the values that maximize the likelihood of observing the data given the model. The MLE is a common method for estimating the parameters of a VAR model. The idea is to maximize the likelihood function of the VAR model, which is typically assumed to follow a multivariate normal distribution.

The likelihood function for a VAR (p) model is presented in equation 1.

$$L(\theta | Y) = (2\pi)^{-nT/2} |\Sigma|^{-T/2} \exp(-1/2 * \text{tr}(\Sigma^{-1} * S)) \text{-----eqn.1}$$

Where:

θ represents the parameters of the VAR model (including the coefficients and covariance matrix),

Y is the matrix of observed data,

n is the number of variables,

T is the number of observations,

Σ is the covariance matrix of the error terms, and

S is the sample covariance matrix of the residuals.

In line with Townsend (2006), financial products and investments are conceptualized as determinants of sustainable growth in the context of efficient financial services and credit intermediation to the real sectors, which activate sustainable economic services and enhance sustainable economic outcomes. This relationship is specified based on this study's chosen variables in the Likelihood Function and Log-Likelihood Function in equations 2 and 3, while the model is specified in equation 4, respectively.

$$L(\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \sigma^2 | \text{RGDPpc}, \text{GB}, \text{GC}, \text{GI}, \text{EI}, \text{REP}, \text{GHG}, \text{RQ}) = \prod [1/\sqrt{(2\pi\sigma^2)}] * \exp[-(\text{RGD Ppci} - \beta_0 - \beta_1\text{GBi} - \beta_2\text{GCi} - \beta_3\text{GIi} - \beta_4\text{EIi} - \beta_5\text{REPi} - \beta_6\text{GHGi} - \beta_7\text{RQi})^2 / (2\sigma^2)] \text{-----eqn.2}$$

To simplify the calculation, the log-likelihood function was used.

$$\log L(\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \sigma^2 | \text{RGDPpc}, \text{GB}, \text{GC}, \text{GI}, \text{EI}, \text{REP}, \text{GHG}, \text{RQ}) = -n/2 * \log(2\pi) - n/2 * \log(\sigma^2) - 1/(2\sigma^2) * \sum (\text{RGDPpci} - \beta_0 - \beta_1\text{GBi} - \beta_2\text{GCi} - \beta_3\text{GIi} - \beta_4\text{EIi} - \beta_5\text{REPi} - \beta_6\text{GHGi} - \beta_7\text{RQi})^2 \text{-----eqn.3}$$

$$\text{RGDPpc} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{GB} + \beta_2\text{GC} + \beta_3\text{GI} + \beta_4\text{EI} + \beta_5\text{REP} + \beta_6\text{GHG} + \beta_7\text{RQ} + \varepsilon \text{-----eqn.4}$$

RGDPpc: Real Gross Domestic Product per capita (Nigerian Naira per capita)

GB: Green Bond issuance (USD million)

GC: Green Credit provision (USD million)

GI: Green Insurance premiums (USD million)

EI: Eco-Innovation index (index score)

REP: Renewable Energy Production (Gigawatt-hours, GWh)

GHG: Greenhouse Gas emissions (million tons of CO2 equivalents, MtCO2e)

RQ: Regulatory Quality Index (index score)

ε : Error term, assumed to be normally distributed with mean 0 and variance σ^2

n : is the sample size.

The MLEs of the parameters were found by maximizing the log-likelihood function with respect to $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7$, and σ^2 using numerical optimization methods.

The coefficients ($\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7$) represent the change in RGDPpc associated with a one-unit change in the respective independent variable, holding all other variables constant. The significance of each coefficient can be tested using t-tests or p-values.

A vector autoregressive (VAR) model was employed in this study to estimate the data because there was no co-integration (Engle & Granger, 1987). This was followed by Granger causality tests to establish causal linkages between variables. Another analysis carried out is Variance Decomposition, and it was done to separate the variation in an endogenous variable into component shocks to the VAR. Variance decomposition gives information on the relative importance of each random innovation in influencing the variables in the VAR.

Table 3.1 – Description, identifier, measurement, expected signs, and sources of data

Variable	Identifier	Description and Justification	<i>a priori</i> signs	Source
Real gross domestic product per capita	RGDPpc	RGDP pc(proxy for Sustainable economic development) is the sum of gross value added by all resident producers in the economy plus any product taxes (minus subsidies) not included in the valuation of output, divided by mid-year population.RGDP pc considers the standard of living and income levels, which are essential for human development and well-being. It captures the overall well-being of a nation.		CBN Statistical Bulletin
Green bond	GB	Green bond is a fixed-income security designed to support specific climate-related or environmental projects. It may also be referred to as climate bond or sustainable bonds. It represents innovative financing mechanism for environmentally friendly projects.	+	WDI
Green credit	GC	This is loan facilities granted to individuals and organizations for investment in green projects. It is usually initiated by the government to incentivize stakeholders in contributing to environmental preservation and sustainable practices. It encourages lending for green projects, reducing emissions and promoting sustainability.	+	WDI
Green insurance	GI	GI is insurance policy that covers the design, production, and use of sustainable products, or the liability associated with their production and use. They also indemnify against the environmental consequence of potential climate change decisions or indecisions of executives. It provides risk mitigation and management for green investments.	+	WDI and NIID
Renewable Energy Production	REP	REP relates to money expended in the production or generation of energy from natural resources, such as sunlight, wind, geothermal, hydropower, ocean, and biomass (wood, charcoal, and dung). It is a key aspect of reducing greenhouse gas emissions.	+	WDI and NCDC
Eco-innovation	EI	EI relates to a company's ability to develop and implement a coordinated set of sustainable technologies, products, processes, practices, market approaches and organizational structures that will enhance environmental sustainability. EI drives technological advancements for environmentally friendly projects and its sustainability.	+	WDI
Greenhouse gas emissions	GHG	Changes in atmospheric level due to greenhouse gas emissions from water, forest, and land-use. This factor evaluates a company's efforts to monitor, reduce, and offset the impact of pollutants, greenhouse gases, and other harmful substances. GHG is a critical indicator of environmental degradation, influencing policy decisions and green finance effectiveness.	+	WDI and NCDC
Governance	RQ	Governance (regulatory quality) index measures perceptions of government capacity to formulate and implement effective policies and its regulatory ability. This includes environmental regulation and implementation. RQ affects the effectiveness of green finance policies and instruments.	-	WGI

Source: *Authors' 2024*

Findings and Analysis

Table 2: Summary Statistics

Description	LogGDP _{pc}	LogGB	LogGC	LogGI	LogREP	LogEI	LogGHG	LogRQ
Mean	4.2721	0.6748	0.2492	0.5001	0.4852	0.5195	1.3465	0.3432
Maximum	5.1589	0.8169	0.2732	0.6760	0.6159	0.7617	4.9662	1.8660
Minimum	2.9589	0.5327	0.1698	0.3988	0.2589	0.4105	1.0341	-0.7345
Std. Dev.	0.6652	0.0733	0.7693	0.6296	0.9552	0.0327	0.8327	0.5327
Skewness	-0.3875	-0.3324	-0.5457	-0.5810	-0.1897	-0.1938	-0.2438	-0.2038
Kurtosis	1.9145	2.4312	2.3245	2.4764	2.0898	1.1094	2.1094	2.2044
Jarque-Bera	2.0753	0.8932	1.9220	1.8951	1.1344	1.4028	1.4327	1.3432
Probability	0.3542	0.6397	0.3825	0.3876	0.5670	0.2021	0.3421	0.2125
Observations	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23

Source: Authors' computation, 2024

Table 2 revealed that GHG mean value was 1.3465 metric tons per capita. This implies that, on average, each person in Nigeria emits approximately 1.3465 metric tons of GHGs per year. While, EI average value was 0.5195%, it implies that on average, 0.5195% of the total reduction in environmental degradation and GHG emissions is due to eco-innovation in Nigeria. The GB mean value was 0.6748%, which also implies that on average, 0.6748% of the total bond market or total financial investment in Nigeria was invested in Green bonds. The governance index standardized values lie between +2.5 and -2.5, from strong to weak index. The 0.3432 RQ value implies that the RQ in Nigeria is weak. This implies that there is a high rate of corruption and a poor regulatory framework in Nigeria. Similarly, Jarque-Bera statistics with associated probability values are greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the variables are not normally distributed.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis Results

Variables	LogGDP _{pc}	LogGB	LogGC	LogGI	LogREP	LogEI	LogGHG	LogRQ
LogGDP _{pc}	1.000							
LogGB	0.901	1.000						
LogGC	0.912	0.268	1.000					
LogGI	0.932	0.355	0.945	1.000				
LogREP	0.935	0.357	0.891	0.933	1.000			
LogEI	0.723	0.354	0.828	0.818	0.890	1.000		
LogGHG	0.960	0.967	0.960	0.989	0.891	0.988	1.000	
LogRQ	-0.855	-0.878	-0.877	-0.887	0.876	0.509	-0.674	1.000

Source: Authors' computation, 2024

Table 3 indicated that green bond, green credit, green insurance, renewable energy production, co-innovation, and greenhouse gas emissions were positively correlated with real GDP per capita but regulatory quality was negatively correlated with real GDP per capita.

Table 4: Unit Root Test Result

Variable	ADF value (Level)	ADF value (1 st difference)	5% critical value	Order of integrate	Remarks
RGDP _{pc}	-2.0437	-6.9420	-2.9862	I(1)	Stationary
GB	-1.9895	-5.8997	-2.9862	I(1)	Stationary
GC	-2.0869	-4.9092	-2.9862	I(1)	Stationary
GI	-2.0132	-5.2291	-2.9862	I(1)	Stationary
REP	-1.9826	-5.6949	-2.9862	I(1)	Stationary
EI	-2.0912	-5.5275	-2.9862	I(1)	Stationary
GHG	-2.0209	-5.8092	-2.9862	I(1)	Stationary
RQ	-1.8925	-4.7062	-2.9862	I(1)	Stationary

Source: Authors' computation, 2024

The ADF unit root test result indicated that variables were not stationary at levels but they however, became stationary at first difference (table 4). Co-integration between the variables was investigated using Johansen's approach.

Table 5: Johansen Co-integration Test Result

Hypothesized No. of CE	Eigen value	Trace statistics	0.05 critical value	Prob.
None	0.86660	71.10901	89.81889	0.5537
At most 1	0.67381	42.74963	57.85613	0.5146
At most 2	0.61688	35.74275	44.79707	0.4681
At most 3	0.36814	27.75789	35.49471	0.4043
At most 4	0.12299	12.28093	18.84147	0.3714
At most 5	0.10238	8.26084	12.86346	0.3538
At most 6	0.08427	4.82917	7.96746	0.3142
At most 7	0.04258	0.68092	1.92357	0.2509

Source: Authors' computation, 2024

Table 5 indicated that there is no co-integrating equation among the variables, which implied that there is no long run relationship. Since the variables are not co-integrated, the Restricted VAR Model was used in modeling the selected variables. Determination of optimum lag by comparing every lag to the criteria used is the first step taken in VAR Model checking, which is very important in time series data analysis.

Table 6: Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	29.33420	NA	2.28e-07	-1.10631	-0.86069	-1.03296
1	138.7304	162.9173*	7.79e-10	-6.82549	-4.37379	-6.40739
2	167.5955	94.30580	7.37e-10*	-7.12729*	-5.46131*	-6.85635*
3	183.5467	43.62722	7.64e-10	-6.54018	-5.06391	-5.78241
4	201.8791	12.90365	8.21e-10	-4.73601	-3.89325	-5.23863

Source: Authors' computation, 2024

Table 6 indicated that the lag optimum is at lag2 by the selection criteria of the AIC, FPE, HQ, and SC. VAR is conducted to check the speed of adjustment from short-run dynamics to their long-run static disposition and the result is presented in table 7.

Table 7: Vector Autoregressive Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.608215	0.551865	2.914146	0.0251
Log(GB(-1))	0.157607	0.053968	2.920379	0.0212
Log(GC(-1))	0.199639	0.091517	2.181442	0.0426
Log(GI(-1))	0.163775	0.052509	1.718989	0.0589
Log(REP(-1))	0.153607	0.063572	2.411627	0.0360
Log(EI(-1))	0.293371	0.094798	3.094696	0.0117
Log(GHG(-1))	-0.335314	0.103893	-3.227494	0.0086
Log(RQ(-1))	-0.248763	0.069038	-3.603263	0.0054
R-squared	0.554246	Mean dependent var	0.076512	
Adj. R ²	0.286794	S.D. dependent var	0.042362	
F-statistics	2.072317	Durbin-Watson stat	2.058100	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001995			

Source: Authors Computation, 2024

The estimated regression equation is presented in equation 5.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LogRGDP}_{pc} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogGB} + \beta_2 \text{LogGC} + \beta_3 \text{LogGI} + \beta_4 \text{LogREP} + \beta_5 \text{LogEI} + \beta_6 \text{LogGHG} + \beta_7 \text{LogRQ} \\ &+ u_t \\ \text{LogRGDP}_{pc} &= 1.608215 + 0.157607\text{GB} + 0.199639\text{GC} + 0.163775\text{GI} + 0.153607\text{REP} + 0.293371\text{EI} + \\ &0.335314\text{GHG} - 0.248772\text{RQ} + u_t \dots \dots \dots \text{eqn.5} \end{aligned}$$

The result obtained in this study indicated that green bonds had a positive and significant impact on RGDP_{pc} (coefficient of 0.157607 and a p-value of 0.0212). This implies that for every 1% increase in green bond investment in Nigeria, real gross domestic product per capita is expected to increase by approximately 0.157607%. The coefficient suggest that policies supporting in green infrastructure, and green financing, such as tax incentives, or subsidies for green bonds, can have a positive impact on sustainable economic development. Similarly, green credit (coefficient of 0.199639 and a p-value of 0.0426) had positive and significant impact on real gross domestic product per capita, and it means that for every 1% increase in green credit lending in Nigeria, real gross domestic product per capita is expected to increase by approximately 0.199639%.

Green insurance (coefficient of 0.163775 and a p-value of 0.0589), however, had a positive but non-significant impact on RGDP_{pc} in Nigeria, and it implies that for every 1% increase in green insurance premiums or coverage in Nigeria, real gross domestic product per capita is expected to increase by approximately 0.163775%. Government can leverage on this and subsidize insurance premiums, invest in climate resilience measures, such as flood defenses, renewable energy production, and green infrastructure, and encourage insurance companies to offer green insurance products that can reduce the impact of climate related risks.

Renewable energy production (coefficient of 0.153607 and a p-value of 0.0360), has a positive and significant impact on RGDP_{pc} . The implication of this is that for every 1% increase in renewable energy production in Nigeria, real gross domestic product per capita increases by 0.153607 units.

Similarly, Eco-innovation (coefficient of 0.293371 and a p-value of 0.0117), has a positive and significant impact on RGDP_{pc} . It corroborates with (Mahmood, Zhao, Lou & Geng, 2022), who show that, when firms apply eco-innovation in the form of energy transition from non-renewable to renewable energy, using energy-efficient technologies and effective wastage management, they get rid of the waste from manufacturing or other business operations.

Greenhouse gas emissions (coefficient of -0.335314 and a p-value of 0.0086), had significant but negative impact on RGDP_{pc} . This implies that GHG emissions are high in Nigeria and the current level GHG emissions is unsustainable. The coefficient is negative, which means that for unit increase in GHG emissions, real gross domestic product per capita decreases by 0.335314 units. This suggests that reducing GHG emissions can lead to an increase in real GDP per capita. Likewise, The regulatory quality (coefficient of -0.248763 and a p-value of 0.0054), was significant and negative, a 1% increase in regulatory quality is associated with a 0.248763% decrease in real GDP per capita. This implies that the RQ index in Nigeria is weak.

Table 8: VAR (Least Squares (Gauss Newton/Marquardt steps) Result

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C(1)	-0.008656	0.054292	-0.159434	0.0659
C(2)	0.260944	0.210541	1.239396	0.2342
C(3)	0.062967	0.232368	0.270982	0.7901
C(4)	-0.013892	0.062534	-0.222148	0.8272
C(5)	-0.062366	0.058318	-1.069399	0.3018
C(6)	0.038600	0.097418	0.396237	0.6975
C(7)	0.142890	0.071829	1.989325	0.0652
C(8)	0.010403	0.022391	0.464606	0.6489
C(9)	0.004861	0.030083	0.161582	0.8738
C(10)	0.041158	0.020374	2.020158	0.0616

Source: Authors' computation, 2024

Table 8 revealed that ECM (-1) was consistent by assuming a negative value. The result of the coefficient of the stochastic variable suggests that there was no long run effect because the ECM was not significant and could not correct deviation from the long-run equilibrium relationship between $RGDP_{pc}$ and the explanatory variables. The coefficient indicates a speedy adjustment of 0.87% per annum. This implies that following short-run disequilibrium in the system, only 0.87% of adjustment to the long-run takes place within one year.

Table 9: Variance Decomposition

LogRGDP _{pc} Period	S.E.	LogRGDP _{pc}	LogGB	LogGC	LogGI	LogREP	LogEI	LogGHG	LogRQ
1	0.0724	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	0.0770	80.42	0.20	2.47	2.32	2.18	2.90	8.67	0.84
3	0.0809	72.69	1.19	3.60	2.35	4.14	3.64	9.63	2.76
4	0.0832	68.28	1.33	5.69	3.95	5.56	5.59	6.80	2.80
5	0.0844	60.13	1.80	7.78	5.90	7.15	6.05	8.19	3.00
6	0.0855	57.22	2.06	7.19	5.80	7.62	6.83	9.89	3.39
7	0.0859	56.48	2.51	7.56	6.06	8.09	5.60	10.19	3.51
8	0.0863	53.05	3.10	7.60	6.54	8.52	5.61	11.51	4.07
9	0.0864	50.16	3.58	8.00	7.14	9.07	5.72	11.80	4.53
10	0.0864	49.01	4.12	8.15	7.17	9.17	5.75	12.03	4.60

Sources: Authors, computation, 2024

The forecast error variance decomposition is the percentage of variance of the error made in forecasting a variable due to a specific shock. Usually, for the initial period, forecast error variance is due to own shock. However, as the lagged effects begin to manifest, the percentage of the effect of other shocks increases over time while the own shocks decrease. GDP_{pc} own shock in table 9 at first was 100 per cent, as expected. In the second period, forecast error due to shocks from other variables was 19.58 per cent, while forecast errors due to own shock was 80.42 per cent. Based on the variance decomposition results, the predominant source of variation in GDP_{pc} is greenhouse gas emissions, followed by renewable energy production, green credit, green insurance, eco-innovation, regulatory quality, and green bond, respectively.

Table 10: VAR Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
Log GB does not Granger Cause Log RGDP _{pc} Log RGDP _{pc} does not Granger Cause Log GB	23	3.8613 0.2861	0.0424 0.7540
Log GC does not Granger Cause Log RGDP _{pc} Log RGDP _{pc} does not Granger Cause Log GC	23	3.4130 2.0718	0.0438 0.1183
Log GI does not Granger Cause Log RGDP _{pc} Log RGDP _{pc} does not Granger Cause LogGI	23	4.6080 5.4474	0.0340 0.0107
Log REP does not Granger Cause LogRGDP _{pc} Log RGDP _{pc} does not Granger Cause LogREP	23	5.0363 3.7071	0.0169 0.0436
Log EI does not Granger Cause LogRGDP _{pc} Log RGDP _{pc} does not Granger Cause LogEI	23	3.6261 3.5152	0.0440 0.0443
LogGHG does not Granger Cause Log RGDP _{pc} LogRGDP _{pc} does not Granger Cause Log GHG	23	6.1833 5.2373	0.0038 0.0115
Log RQ does not Granger Cause Log RGDP _{pc} LogRGDP _{pc} does not Granger Cause LogRQ	23	0.7833 0.5822	0.5294 0.6174

Sources: Authors' computation, 2024

Table 10 showed a unidirectional causal flow from GB and GC to real gross domestic product per capita, indicating that GB and GC can finance sustainable projects, contributing to environmentally friendly economic growth and development. A bi-directional causality exists between GI, REP, EI, GHG, and real GDP per capita. The implications are that GI, REP, EI, GHG enhance real GDP per capita, and vice versa.

5. Discussion

This study examined the relationship between green financing, greenhouse gas emissions, and sustainable economic development in Nigeria using a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model. Key findings include:

Positive impacts: Green bonds, green credit, renewable energy production, and eco-innovation all significantly contribute to sustainable economic development.

Green insurance: Had a positive but insignificant impact.

Negative impacts: Greenhouse gas emissions and governance index negatively affect sustainable economic development.

The study emphasized the critical role of green financing in reducing emissions and supporting environment-friendly investments, which in turn promotes economic growth. It also highlighted the importance of strong governance in maximizing the effectiveness of green financing policies. Sustainable businesses benefit from green finance through lower capital costs, improved reputation, and access to new markets.

The result obtained in this study indicated that green bonds had a positive and significant impact on RGDP_{pc}. This implies that for every 1% increase in green bond investment in Nigeria, real gross domestic product per capita is expected to increase by approximately 0.157607%. The coefficient suggest that policies supporting in green infrastructure, and green financing, such as tax incentives, or subsidies for green bonds, can have a positive impact on sustainable economic development. The result corroborated with (Maltais and Nykvist 2020); and (Risaland Joshi, 2018), who found that the issuance of green bond enhances the financial capacity of businesses and allows them to use energy-efficient resources and innovative technologies in production and other business activities which enhances economic growth.

Similarly, green credit (coefficient of 0.199639 and a p-value of 0.0426) had positive and significant impact on real gross domestic product per capita, and it means that for every 1% increase in green credit lending in Nigeria, real gross domestic product per capita is expected to increase by approximately 0.199639%.

Policymakers can design targeted interventions to increase green credit allocation, focusing on sectors with high growth potentials, and developing green finance guidelines, standards, and reporting frameworks. The result is in line with (Zhang and Wang, 2021) who discovered that green credit fosters sustainability in business development and (Taghizadeh-Hesary, Yoshino, and Phoumin, 2021), who found that green credits facilities enable firms tackle issue of GHG emissions at reduced cost of capital. Green insurance however, had a positive but non-significant impact on $RGDP_{pc}$ in Nigeria, and it implies that for every 1% increase in green insurance premiums or coverage in Nigeria, real gross domestic product per capita is expected to increase by approximately 0.163775%. Government can leverage on this and subsidize insurance premiums, invest in climate resilience measures, such as flood defenses, renewable energy production, and green infrastructure, and encourage insurance companies to offer green insurance products that can reduce the impact of climate related risks. This result is in tandem with findings of Mills (2009) who recorded that availability of data on the effectiveness of green insurance is often limited, making it challenging to assess their impact and determine best practices; and the research result of (Hou and Wang, 2022) who argued that there is lack of comprehensive data on the effectiveness of green insurance initiatives and that some insurance policies have not yet addressed climate risk practices. This implies that regulatory and policy uncertainties hinder the adoption of green insurance schemes in Nigeria, and this could be the reason its impact was not significant.

Renewable energy production, has a positive and significant impact on $RGDP_{pc}$. The implication of this is that for every 1% increase in renewable energy production in Nigeria, real gross domestic product per capita increases by 0.153607 units. Investment in renewable energy sources like solar, wind, and hydroelectric power will boost energy production and enhance sustainable economic growth. This lends credence to the results of (Kirikkaleli and Adebayo, 2021), who state that, when there is a focus on the production of renewable energy to meet emerging requirements of both domestic and commercial entities, it controls CO_2 emissions, as the production of renewable energy absorbs carbon dioxide from the air, excessive water from the soil, and heat from the atmosphere. Similarly, Eco-innovation (coefficient of 0.293371 and a p-value of 0.0117), has a positive and significant impact on $RGDP_{pc}$. It corroborates with (Mahmood, Zhao, Lou&Geng, 2022), who show that, when firms apply eco-innovation in the form of energy transition from non-renewable to renewable energy, using energy- efficient technologies and effective wastage management, they get rid of the waste from manufacturing or other business operations. Greenhouse gas emissions had significant but negative impact on $RGDP_{pc}$. This implies that GHG emissions are high in Nigeria and the current level GHG emissions is unsustainable. The coefficient is negative, which means that for unit increase in GHG emissions, real gross domestic product per capita decreases. This suggests that reducing GHG emissions can lead to an increase in real GDP per capita. The result collaborates with that of (Ogbuabor and Egwuchukwu, 2017) that found that CO_2 emissions affected economic growth adversely in Nigeria. Likewise, The regulatory quality (coefficient of -0.248763 and a p-value of 0.0054), was significant and negative, a 1% increase in regulatory quality is associated with a 0.248763% decrease in real GDP per capita. This implies that the RQ index in Nigeria is weak. This is in agreement with the findings of (Odili and Onyele, 2023); (Salih and Abdullah, 2017); (Ondrej and Agata, 2015) who discovered that increasing rate of corruption and poor regulatory framework hampers effective regulation and policy implementation.

The result also showed a unidirectional causal flow from GB and GC to real gross domestic product per capita, indicating that GB and GC can finance sustainable projects, contributing to environmentally friendly economic growth and development. A bi-directional causality exists between GI, REP, EI, GHG, and real GDP per capita. The implications are that GI, REP, EI, GHG enhance real GDP per capita, and vice versa. Their combine effects will lead to reduction in environmental risks, and promotion of eco-innovation (O'Donohoe et., 2019), contributes to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, mitigating climate change impact on real GDP per capita (IPCC, 2018), green insurance supports renewable energy production by managing risks associated with climate change (Wang, et al., 2020). However, there is no causal linkage between real GDP per capita and regulatory quality. The policy implication is that the regulation of the environment in Nigeria is ineffective and cannot drive sustainable development. The government should therefore reassess its regulatory focus and priorities are as that has the potential to enhance sustainable economic development. The Granger causality analysis there for suggests that increase in green bond, green credit, green insurance, renewable energy production, eco-innovation, and greenhouse gas emissions have the potential of enhancing real GDP per capita, while improvement in RGDP on the other hand, causes green insurance, renewable energy production, eco-innovation, and greenhouse gas emissions in Nigeria

The study recommended that Nigerian policymakers:

- Develop policies to grow the green finance market, such as carbon pricing and clean energy incentives.
- Strengthen regulatory frameworks to support green financing.
- Foster eco-innovation and ensure transparency and accountability.
- Make green insurance mandatory for enterprises with significant environmental impact and incentivize insurance companies to develop relevant products.

Limitations include the use of secondary data focused on Nigeria, potential gaps in the independent variables used, and the generalization of greenhouse gas emissions as a single variable. Future research could explore green financing in smart agriculture and its links to health outcomes.

6. Conclusion

The study concludes that Nigerian policymakers should expand the green finance market by implementing policies like carbon pricing and clean energy incentives, strengthening regulatory frameworks, promoting transparency, and fostering eco-innovation for sustainable economic growth. Also, the government should mandate green insurance for environmentally impactful enterprises, incentivize insurers to develop climate-related products, provide subsidies or tax incentives to lower premiums, and establish supportive regulations for green insurance.

Future Perspectives

Green financing is projected to shift from a specialized tool to a core feature of modern financial systems. The growth of green bonds, sustainability-linked loans, and climate funds will strengthen capital markets and attract long-term investors. These instruments will increasingly fund large-scale infrastructure, renewable energy, and climate-resilient development projects. Future green finance frameworks will align more closely with global climate commitments and national development priorities. This alignment will integrate economic growth with emissions-reduction and environmental-protection goals. Technological innovations such as fintech, blockchain, and data analytics will enhance transparency and accountability in green investments. Digital solutions will also reduce green-washing risks and expand access to green finance for SMEs and underserved groups. Stronger policy frameworks, including clear taxonomies and mandatory sustainability disclosures, will guide effective capital allocation. Green financing will adopt a more inclusive approach by promoting job creation, social equity, and poverty reduction. In the long term, green finance will support structural transformation toward resilient, low-carbon, and sustainable economic growth.

Future Scope

The scope of future research can be expanded by extending the analysis beyond Nigeria to include other Sub-Saharan African countries or emerging economies with similar environmental and financial structures. Such comparative studies would provide broader insights into how green financing influences greenhouse gas emissions and sustainable economic development across different institutional and policy environments. Future studies may also consider a longer time horizon or more recent data to capture the evolving nature of green finance instruments, climate policies, and technological innovations in renewable energy and low-carbon development.

Future Investigation

Future investigations could further deepen this study by incorporating additional indicators of sustainable development, such as inclusive growth, employment generation, energy access, and social welfare outcomes. There is also scope to disaggregate green finance into specific components such as green bonds, renewable energy financing, climate adaptation finance, and private sector green investments to assess their individual and comparative impacts on emissions reduction and economic sustainability. In addition, future research may adopt alternative methodological approaches, including micro-level or sector-specific analyses, to better understand the transmission channels through which green finance affects environmental and economic outcomes.

Potential Research Extensions

Future studies can disaggregate green financing effects across sectors to capture heterogeneous outcomes, especially in developing and emerging economies. Firm-level analyses should examine how size, ownership, governance, and technological capacity influence the effectiveness of green finance. Research can extend by integrating institutional quality and governance indicators to assess how regulatory strength shapes green finance outcomes. Incorporating environmental performance measures will help evaluate the joint economic and ecological impacts of green financing and limit green-washing concerns. Emerging digital financial technologies offer new research avenues on access, efficiency, and accountability in green finance delivery. Methodological extensions using causal and non-linear models, alongside standardized green finance indices, can improve robustness and policy relevance.

Limitations

Existing literature is constrained by limited and unreliable green finance data, especially in developing and emerging economies. Heavy reliance on aggregate-level analyses masks firm-level, sectoral, and regional differences in green financing impacts. Many studies use static or short-term models that fail to capture long-run dynamics and adequately address endogeneity issues. Institutional and regulatory factors influencing green finance effectiveness are often underrepresented in empirical frameworks. Research remains narrowly focused on environmental outcomes, with limited attention to inclusive development and access for SMEs and vulnerable groups.

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